

Site: SPHINX
TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number ⑥

Progress of Excavation _____

Locus Description BLUE "GRANITE DUST"

Location in Square Small Patch showing for NE Corner, somewhat
along edge N Balk

Under Locus ⑤ BUFF-WHITE GYPSUM Over Locus _____

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____

